

Oscillopolarographic Reversibility of Iron, Cobalt and Nickel at the Surface of Mercury Drop in Dimethylsulfoxide

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D. C. and A. C. polarised voltametric studies of Fe, Co and Ni in dimethylsulfoxide have been carried out using Hg-pool and S. C. E. as non-polarised reference electrodes. The chemical reaction of Fe^{3+} with DMSO in presence of LiClO_4 as supporting electrolyte could not give any polarographic wave in D. C. voltammetry but Q-values have been found in oscillopolarography.

In recent years the popularity of non-aqueous solvents as reaction promoters and reaction media has vastly expanded. Accordingly, opportunity and interest in characterising solvent-solute interaction has also increased. Kambara¹ and Matsuda² were the first to derive the equation of the oscillopolarographic curve but Micka³ proposed an approximate theory which was in good agreement. The curve dE/dt vs $f(E)$ is suited for comparison of theory and experiment. In pure supporting electrolytes such as aqueous KOH or KClO_4 the theoretical curves are in good accord with the experimental ones. But in non-aqueous medium, apart from iR drop the surface activity of organic molecules complicates the organic electrode reactions and artefacts are sometimes formed. In the present study an electrochemical approach has been used to gather data, specially polarographic half wave potentials in D.C. polarography and Q-values in oscillopolarography. The determination depends upon the process occurring at the surface of mercury drop.

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical or reagent grade B.D.H., Pfizer or S. Merck quality.

(i) *Polarographic measurement*: D.C. polarograms were taken with an automatic three-electrode Radelkis Hungarian polarograph OH-102. The capillary having characteristics $m=4.709$ mg/sec. and $t=1.86$ sec. (at 45 cm of Hg pressure in 0.1 M LiClO_4 in the open circuit) was used throughout unless otherwise mentioned. The polarograph was run at a speed of 8 min for the voltage range of 2 volts at damping 3.

Fig. 1. R_1 = Variable resistance in steps, 1 M Ω
 R_2 = Potentiometer in steps, 50 K Ω
 R_3 = 20 K Ω , R_4 = 1 K Ω , G = Selenium rectifier
 C_1 and C_2 = 4 μf , C_3 = 8 μf , C_4 = 0.03 μf .

(ii) *Voltage-controlled A. C. oscillopolarographic measurement*: An electrical circuit used for polarising an electrode with a controlled alternating current was fabricated based on Heyrovsky and Kalvoda⁴ with a little modification. The basic scheme of the circuit is given in Fig. 1.

To photograph a stable oscillopolarogram, a hanging mercury drop due to Underkofler and Shain⁵ was used. The stabilized oscillopolarograms were photographed on "Indu" film (400 ASA/27 DIN) with an Agfa Camera having a close-up lens. The time of exposure was about 4-5 seconds. Systronic D.C. Oscilloscope 505 D (Dual trace) was employed for observation and recording of oscillopolarograms.

Results and Discussion

(i) *Effects of electrodes*: In D.C. polarography the voltage-current curves using LiClO_4 and LiCl as supporting electrolytes in DMSO have been obtained using dropping mercury electrode in conjunction with (i) Hg-pool and (ii) S.C.E. Some representative curves are shown in Fig. 2.

In case of Fe(III) cation no polarographic wave appeared with S.C.E. as reference electrode but one wave at $E_{1/2} = -0.50\text{v}$ was observed with Hg-pool as reference electrode.

(ii) *D.C. reversibility*: The values of slopes based upon diffusion controlled current by plotting $\log(i_d - i)/i$ vs potential were recorded. These values appear very much higher (except, to some extent, in cases of Fe^{2+} and Co^{2+}) than those found in the aqueous system. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} and h of the D.C. polarographic reduction waves in 0.1 M LiClO_4 and LiCl of Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Ni^{2+} indicate the process to be diffusion controlled only in case of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} (first wave) and Co^{2+} (second wave) in LiCl . Kinetic and adsorption processes appear to be operative along with the diffusion controlled reduction.

(iii) *Oscillopolarographic reversibility*: In oscillopolarography the time course of polarizing current, $i = i_0 \sin \omega t + i_1$

Fig. 2a. Voltage-current curves in DMSO at dropping mercury electrode with S.C.F. in 0.1M LiClO₄ after purging with N₂: (1) Fe²⁺, (1') Fe³⁺, (2) Co²⁺, (2') Co³⁺ and (3) Ni²⁺.

Fig. 2b. Voltage-current curves in DMSO at dropping mercury electrode with Hg-pool in 0.1M LiCl after purging with N₂: (1) Fe²⁺, (1') Fe³⁺, (2) Co²⁺, (2') Co³⁺ and (3) Ni²⁺.

where i_1 = D.C. component and $i = V_0/R_1 \sin \omega t$ and V_0 = amplitude of the A.C. voltage from the transformer.

This current passing across the solution is greater than in D.C. polarography and in non-aqueous systems

the value of potential will be too small to be observed. Hence the compensation of internal resistance becomes necessary. The device designated by Vogel⁶ was introduced for the compensation of iR in the basic voltage controlled A.C. polarised electric current. In case of oscillopolarographic reversibility potentials of the cathodic and anodic (the upper and the lower of a cyclic curve) incisions have to coincide and the shape and approximately the depths of both incisions should be similar (Fig. 3).

In D.C. polarography it is sufficient if the equilibrium is established during a time comparable with the drop time (about 2-3 sec.). In oscillopolarography the reversible processes must reach equilibrium much more quickly because one cycle lasts only 1/50 sec (A.C. of 50 Hz.). Sometimes, however the opposite behaviour is observed which has been explained either in terms of consecutive reactions or adsorption. These consecutive reactions which cannot take place during the short time available in oscillopolarography, cause insufficient mobility in D.C. polarography. Accordingly, in the D.C. polarographic method no wave has been observed whereas cathodic and anodic incisions have been recorded in oscillopolarography.

(iv) *Q-values* : According to Heyrovsky⁴ the quotient (*Q-value*) is more useful than the value of potential which gives the relative position of the indentation on the derivative curve $dE/dt = f(E)$ measured from the positive limiting potential (left hand side of the upper and right hand side of the lower part of a cyclic photograph). The *Q-values* vary between 0 and 1 and are independent of the reference electrode. Accordingly, authors have given the *Q-values* of all the indentations including thorn-like on the both parts viz. cathodic and anodic in Table 1.

Differences in these values particularly between the cathodic and anodic parts may be attributed to some

Fig. 3. Oscillopolarograms in DMSO + 0.1M LiClO₄ in presence of (1) nil, (2) Fe²⁺, (3) Fe³⁺, (4) Co²⁺, (5) Co³⁺ and (6) Ni²⁺, $i_0 = 0.92 \text{ ma/cm}^2$ and $i_1 = -0.083 \text{ ma/cm}^2$. Potential axis range = 0.55v.

TABLE 1—Q-VALUES

System (Uncompensated)	Cathodic					Anodic				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
DMSO+0.1M LiClO ₄ and Fe ⁺⁺	0.22	0.64	0.74			0.28	0.82	0.88		
Fe ⁺⁺	0.28	0.66	0.73			0.28	0.73	0.80		
Co ⁺⁺	0.27	0.70				0.28	0.73			
Co ⁺⁺	0.24	0.66				0.27	0.8			
Ni ⁺⁺	0.19	0.47				—	—	—		
Ni ⁺⁺	0.19	0.66	0.73			0.2	0.84	0.9		
System Compensated										
DMSO+0.1M LiClO ₄ and Fe ⁺⁺	0.19	0.33	0.48	0.7		0.19	0.33	0.48	0.7	
Fe ⁺⁺	0.2	0.35	0.47	0.68		0.2	0.35	0.5	0.7	
Co ⁺⁺	0.19	0.24	0.31	0.45	0.6	0.19	0.24	0.33	0.45	0.66
Co ⁺⁺	0.18	0.32	0.43	0.64		0.18	0.32	0.5	0.7	
Co ⁺⁺	0.1	0.17	0.35	0.55	0.85	0.07	0.15	0.35	0.55	0.85
Ni ⁺⁺	0.09	0.18	0.44	0.5	0.8	0.09	0.18	0.44	0.5	0.73
DMSO+0.1M LiCl and Fe ⁺⁺	0.12	0.44	0.68			0.12	0.44	0.68		
Fe ⁺⁺	0.17	0.37	0.57	0.73	—	0.2	0.37	0.53	0.73	—
Co ⁺⁺	0.12	0.42	0.6	0.79		0.12	0.48	0.69	0.83	
Co ⁺⁺	0.1	0.2	0.46	0.65		0.1	0.2	0.46	0.67	
Co ⁺⁺	0.2	0.34	0.5	0.68		0.2	0.36	0.54	0.72	0.86
Ni ⁺⁺	0.14	0.24	0.41	0.62	0.8	0.14	0.27	0.48	0.7	

irreversibility and other processes occurring at the surface of mercury drop more likely adsorption (see the lower portion of photograph No. 5) and formation of insolubles.

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References

1. T. KAMBARA, *Leyhold Polarograph Ber.*, 1954, 2, 59.
2. H. MATSUDA, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1956, 60, 617.
3. K. MICKA, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1957, 206, 354.
4. J. HEYROVSKY and R. KALVODA, "Oscillographische polarographic mit Wechselstrom", Academic, Berlin, 1960.
5. W. L. UNDERKOFER and L. SHAIN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 1966.
6. J. VOGEL, *Chem. zvesti.*, 1954, 8, 897.